

Some Heteropoly Salts of Tellurium

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Ammonium tellurato-tetramolybdate, $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 4\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been prepared; its properties have been studied and composition has been determined by analytical methods. Silver, barium, lead, uranyl, and cerous salts have been prepared from the ammonium salt, analysed, and their formations confirmed by conductometric titrations.

Gibbs¹ and Klein² observed the formation of complex molybdotellurites and tungstotellurites and Pechard³ isolated molybdoselenites. Miolati⁴ seems to be the first who studied the salts of the complex heteropoly acids of molybdenum and tellurium and prepared the compound of apparent formula $\text{Te}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot \text{K}_{10} \cdot 12\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or possibly $\text{TeO}_3 \cdot \text{K}_5 \cdot \text{H} \cdot 6\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Meloche and Woodstock⁵ isolated two ammonium molybdotellurates: $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 6\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 6\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Hansen⁶ prepared the potassium salt $3\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 6\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Thomsen⁷, the sodium molybdotellurate, $3\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 6\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 22\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the composition of which was confirmed by Wood and Carlson⁸, who also studied the preparation of rubidium and caesium molybdotellurates. Dyess⁹ reported the composition of the lithium salt to be $3\text{Li}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 6\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the reactions between molybdic and telluric acids. This communication records the results of the preparation and analysis of a new molybdotellurate and its reaction with silver, lead, uranyl, and cerous nitrates and barium chloride, leading to the formation of the respective molybdotellurates. Their formation has also been confirmed by conductometric titrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium Tellurato-molybdate.—Telluric and molybdic acids were taken in the ratio of 1:4 and a slight excess of ammonia was added. The solution was refluxed for 4 hr. and then concentrated. It was made slightly acidic with acetic acid and kept in a refrigerator when ammonium tellurato-molybdate separated. It was recrystallised from water two to three times for purification, dried in a vacuum desiccator, and analysed.

Tellurium.—The compound was dissolved in HCl (dil.) and the tellurium content determined by the Lanher-Homerger method¹⁰ in which elementary tellurium was pre-

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3. *Compt. rend.*, 1893, 117, 104.
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5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 171.
6. Unpublished thesis, University of Wisconsin, 1930.
7. Unpublished thesis, University of Wisconsin, 1933.
8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1810.
9. Unpublished thesis, Oklahoma A. and M. College, 1944.
10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 387.

precipitated by the combined action of saturated sulphur dioxide water and hydrazine hydrate solution.

Molybdic Oxide.—The filtrate after determination of tellurium was evaporated to a small bulk on a water bath and was then fumed with H_2SO_4 (conc., ca. 10 ml). The resulting solution was diluted until the acid concentration was about 10%. The molybdenum content was determined by reduction in a Jones reductor and titration with a standard $KMnO_4$ solution.

Ammonia.—The sample was treated with an excess of NaOH solution and the liberated ammonia distilled into a standard solution of HCl. The excess acid was backtitrated against a standard NaOH solution and the results were calculated in terms of $(NH_4)_2O$.

Water.—The percentage of water in ammonium salt was found by difference as the compound began to decompose after heating. In the rest, the compound was heated in an air-oven at 120° to a constant weight and the percentage of water calculated from the loss in weight of the compound (Table I).

TABLE I

	Found.	Calc.
$(NH_4)_2O$	13.75%	13.25%
TeO_3	14.87	14.91
MoO_3	48.11	48.93
H_2O	23.27	22.94

The compound is a white crystalline salt, stable at the room temperature but decomposes, when heated, to a residue containing molybdic oxide and a small amount of tellurium oxide. It is soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents. It is decomposed by dilute acid solution.

The barium, silver, lead, uranyl, and cerium salts were prepared by adding solutions of chloride of barium and nitrates of silver, lead, uranyl, and cerous to the ammonium salt solution. The results are recorded in Table II.

Conductometric Titrations.—0.01Molar solutions of ammonium telluratomolybdate and the titrants (silver nitrate, lead nitrate, barium chloride, uranyl nitrate, and cerous nitrate) were prepared in conductivity water. Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution.

Definite volumes of ammonium salt solution (0.001M), diluted to 60 ml, were taken in a Pyrex beaker, placed on a magnetic stirrer; the cell was dipped properly and the initial conductance recorded by a Mullard conductivity bridge of type E. 7566, direct reading electronic instrument. The titrants were added in small amounts by a microburette, the mixture was stirred well by magnetic stirrer, and the readings were recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle. The end point was obtained graphically by plotting volume of the titrant added against the conductance (Fig. 1).

SOME HETEROPOLY SALTS OF TELLURIUM

375

TABLE II

Tellurate-molybdates.	Formula.	Colour.	%Metallic oxide.		%TeO ₃ .		%MoO ₃ .		%H ₂ O.		
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
Silver	3Ag ₂ O.TeO ₃ .4MoO ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellowish white	Ag ₂ O :	45.81	11.35	11.59	36.84	37.94	4.56	4.74	
Barium	3BaO.TeO ₃ .4MoO ₃ .7H ₂ O	White	BaO :	34.98	13.01	13.13	41.94	43.06	9.23	9.42	
Lead	3PbO.TeO ₃ .4MoO ₃ .6H ₂ O	Dirty white	PbO :	44.83	11.28	11.43	36.42	37.67	7.21	7.06	
Ureayl	3(UO ₂)O.TeO ₃ .4MoO ₃ .11H ₂ O	Yellow	(UO ₂)O :	46.28	47.50	9.68	9.71	30.42	31.87	10.81	11.06
Corium	Co ₂ O ₃ .TeO ₃ .4MoO ₃ .19H ₂ O	Light yellow	Co ₂ O ₃ :	27.34	25.34	13.48	13.56	41.46	44.46	16.35	16.68

Assignment of definite structures to the heteropoly acids and their salts encounters a great difficulty on account of large size of the molecules involved. Their compositions have been arrived at on the basis of analytical results, supported further by conductometric titrations.

FIG. 1

Conductometric titrations of the ammonium salt, $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 4\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, with the titrants having uni, di or trivalent cations were carried out. In all the cases only ammonium ion has been replaced by the cations of the titrant, the rest of the composition remaining the same as is evident from the analysis of Ag, Pb, Ba, uranyl, and cerous salts. The sharp breaks at the molar ratio of ammonium salt to the titrant at 1:6, 1:3, and 1:2 in the case of uni, di, and trivalent cations, respectively, lend support to the formation of the salts reported.

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